

BOOK REVIEWS.

Asthma and Its Radical Treatment. By JAMES ADAMS., M. A., F. R. F. P. S., Hamilton Dispensary Aural Surgeon, Glasgow Royal Infirmary; Pp. 184, with 4 illustrations. Paul B. Hoeber, New York, 1913. Price, \$1.50, net.

The author believes that asthma is primarily a toxemia. This toxemia arises partly in the bowel, partly in the tissues. It arises partly by absorption of nitrogenous poisons resulting from intestinal putrefaction under microbial action; but mainly it is due to an error in nitrogenous metabolism, the result of imperfect oxidation or enzyme action. The toxemia, whether arising in bowel or tissues or both, tends to show itself first as catarrh, later as spasm, in the respiratory tract.

The giving of horse-serum whether diphtheria, antitoxin or otherwise, for the treatment of asthma, as is sometimes done, is to be deprecated, especially where there is idiosyncrasy to eggs, fish, shellfish or horses. Asthma can in most cases be absolutely controlled by due attention to dietary and efficient open-air exercise, including occasional fasting.

The asthmatic paroxysm involves bronchiole spasm and a hyperemia of the mucous membrane. Both result from toxemia. This hyperemic condition may vary from that of the recurrent "bronchitis" of children to "angioneurotic" edema and acute pulmonary edema, according to the nature and amount of the toxemia. It may, especially in children, long precede the onset of typical spasm.

The author admits the value of nasal treatment but holds it subsidiary to the treatment of the toxemia. This toxemia alters the asthmatic so that his condition becomes like a powder magazine; nasal disease is apt to supply sparks which cause the explosions of asthma.

He deprecates the excessive nasal surgery that is so often inflicted on the asthmatic. Cauterization of the septal tubercle is sometimes a valuable temporary procedure, but cauterization of the lower turbinals is an unnecessary addition.

There is a toxemic basis for hay-fever kindred to that of asthma; it seems to be slightly different, favoring the irritant action of certain pollens in the nose and the production of coryza rather than of bronchial spasm, though that also is produced in many cases. The toxemia is the predisposing cause of hay-fever, the pollen the exciting cause.

Adams claims that every case of uncomplicated asthma, properly handled, will improve and most of them will get well. In 100 cases of more than ten years' standing, which he reports in detail, 63 were cured or "practically cured," 30 were improved and 7 not improved.

The treatment advocated is principally dietetic. Care should, however, be taken to establish normal nasal respiration if this be impeded. Not only should the food be limited, in quality, quantity and simplicity, to the actual requirements of the individual, but where the asthma is pronounced the patient must fast one day a week.

Active open-air exercise is necessary. The life of the asthmatic should be much the same as that of the convalescent consumptive; windows open night and day, rooms as free of dust as possible, not less than two hours open-air exercise daily. Medicinally some of the usual formulas are given to relieve the paroxysms, but a mercurial purge is given at least once a week to every patient.

The work shows evidence of painstaking observation and careful analysis of cases observed in the practice of the author. Although lacking experimental confirmation of the toxemic origin of asthma, it merits careful consideration, especially in view of the therapeutic success evidenced in the reported cases.

SCHEPPEGRELL.

The Career of Dr. Weaver. By Mrs. Henry Backus, pp. 379, with illustrations by William Van Dresser. L. C. Page & Co., 1913. Price, \$1.25.

The busy doctor needs recreation even in his literature and he will find this novel, with episodes from the life of a busy, ambitious laryngologist, both interesting and fascinating.